

Comparison Between Laparoscopic Nissen Fundoplication And Partial Anterior Fundoplication In GERD

Mohammed Abdelgilil Elbalshy^{1*}, Soliman Abdelrahman Elshakhs², Hatem Mahmoud Soltan³,
Mohammed Sabry Ammar⁴

¹⁻⁴ Department of general surgery, faculty of medicine, Menoufia university, Shebin El-Kom,
Menoufia, Egypt.

E-mail: : mohammed.balshy@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to compare the efficacy and outcome of laparoscopic Nissen fundoplication versus partial anterior fundoplication in patients with gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). Thirty patients with proven GERD scheduled for laparoscopic antireflux surgery were randomized to either Nissen total or anterior partial fundoplication in the period between October 2012 and October 2014. Mean operative time was significantly shorter in partial anterior group. As regarding to reflux symptoms (heartburn and regurgitation) Nissen was significantly higher in control of reflux symptoms at 3 months but at 6, 12 months Nissen still higher but not significant on the opposite side dysphagia was significantly higher in Nissen group at 3 months, and remained higher at 6, 12 months but not significant, also gas related symptoms were higher in Nissen group all the time of follow up. Objectively esophagitis improved similarly in both groups. Nissen was more superior in improving LES characters, and 24 hour PH parameters. As a result partial anterior fundoplication can be safe effective and simpler alternative procedure for Nissen fundoplication.

Keywords: Gastroesophageal reflux, Nissen, anterior fundoplication.

INTRODUCTION

Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) is a condition which develops when the reflux of stomach contents causes troublesome symptoms and / or complications. (Jerardi et al., 2010). Antireflux surgery may be required if there is severe symptoms or complications of GERD despite adequate medical therapy. (Richter 2009) However, the multiplicity of different antireflux procedures indicates that the ideal operations for this condition haven't been established. Laparoscopic Nissen fundoplication remains the most commonly performed surgical procedure for the treatment of gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), (Hüttl et al., 2002) however the reported incidence of dysphagia and sequelae is relatively high compared to that

with partial fundoplication. (Watson et al., 2004) The goal of the present study is therefore the evaluation of the results after partial anterior fundoplication in comparison to the gold standard technique (laparoscopic Nissen fundoplication).

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Patients:

Thirty patients with symptomatic GERD were randomized to have laparoscopic partial anterior fundoplication or Nissen fundoplication at general surgery department of Menoufia University hospital in the period from October 2012 to October 2014.

Proof of GERD was by typical reflux symptoms of retrosternal burning discomfort and/or acid regurgitation. All patients underwent endoscopy, esophageal manometry, 24 hour PH monitoring. In addition to these investigations response to PPIs was a good sign for the benefit of antireflux surgery. Patients excluded from the study those with previous antireflux surgery, esophageal motility disorders, functional heartburn or those with Barrett's with potential dysplasia.

Methods:

All patients were divided randomly into two groups .Group 'I' had undergone laparoscopic partial anterior fundoplication, while group 'II' had undergone laparoscopic Nissen fundoplication and all patients had been followed at 3, 6 and 12 months the follow up was by clinical examination using a standardized scoring system of reflux symptoms (heartburn, regurgitation and dysphagia) table (1) to facilitate comparison between pre& postoperative results in both groups and between the two groups.

Table (1): Standardized scoring system of reflux symptoms (heartburn, regurgitation and dysphagis)

Symptom	Score	Description
Heartburn :		
None	0	No heartburn.
Minimal	1	Occasional episodes.
Moderate	2	Reason for medical visit.
Severe	3	Interference with daily activities.
Regurgitation:		
None	0	No regurgitation.
Minimal	1	Occasional episodes.
Moderate	2	Predictable on position or straining.
Severe	3	Episodes of pulmonary aspiration manifested by chronic nocturnal cough or recurrent pneumonia
Dysphagia :		
None	0	No dysphagia.
Minimal	1	Occasional episodes.
Moderate	2	Required liquids to clear.
Severe	3	Episodes of food impaction requiring medical treatment.

Follow up with endoscopy was done for all patients after 3months and esophageal

manometry and 24hour PH monitoring were done after 6months. The results of both subjective and objective follow up were tabulated and statistically analyzed.

Operative technique:

In laparoscopic Nissen fundoplication dissection of the esophageal hiatus was done using harmonic scalpel with dissection of short gastric vessels, preservation of the hepatic branch of the vagus nerve where possible, routine posterior hiatal repair and the creation of a short, loose 360° wrap over a 24F nasogastric tube. The wrap was secured with 2/0 "ethibond or non absorbable material" interrupted sutures. The initial steps for laparoscopic anterior fundoplication were the same as those for Nissen fundoplication, commencing with hiatal dissection, esophageal mobilization and posterior hiatal repair. An 180° anterior partial fundoplication was fashioned by fixing the anterior wall of the fundus to the right hiatal pillar and the posterior hiatal repair. The angle of His was accentuated by a suture between the super lateral part of the fundus and the apex of the left hiatal pillar. The short gastric vessels were left intact in laparoscopic anterior fundoplication (LAF).

RESULTS

This study included thirty patients presented for laparoscopic antireflux surgery. Two patients were converted to open procedure one in each group and both were excluded from the study. So each group consisted of 14 patients. The mean operative time for group I was (100±10 min) and was significantly shorter than that of group II (120 ± 19.01 min) table (2).

After 3 months follow up, both Nissen fundoplication and partial anterior fundoplication were significantly effective in controlling reflux symptoms in comparison to preoperative results but Nissen fundoplication is significantly more effective in controlling reflux symptoms than partial anterior fundoplication (P<0.05). On the other hand, there was a significant difference between both groups as regards dysphagia in favor of

partial anterior fundoplication as dysphagia is significantly less with partial anterior fundoplication ($p < 0.05$). After 6 and 12 months follow up, both Nissen fundoplication and partial anterior fundoplication are effective in controlling reflux symptoms with no significant difference between both operations as regards reflux symptoms (heartburn, regurgitation) but dysphagia still higher in group II but is not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) table (3) and (4).

Postoperative endoscopy revealed that esophagitis had improved significantly in both groups nearly to the same extent, 71.1% and 80% in group I and group II respectively ($p > 0.05$). Postoperative manometric study and 24 hour PH monitoring showed that both Nissen and partial anterior fundoplication were effective in improving LES characters and 24 hour PH parameters, however Nissen was more superior

to partial anterior fundoplication table (6) and (7).

DISCUSSION

There were 2 cases (7%) converted to open fundoplication because of bleeding (1 case in Group I and 1 case in Group II). Both of them were excluded from this study. The rate of conversion to open procedure correlates with that of [Watson et al \(1995\)](#), who recorded a conversion rate 8% and [Landreneau et al \(1998\)](#), who recorded a conversion rate 6%. In another study performed by [Baigrie et al \(2005\)](#) recorded (0 %) conversion rate. [Hagedorn et al \(2003\)](#), reported 0% conversion rate. [Kneist et al \(2003\)](#) recorded a conversion rate (1.3%). In the present study the mean operative time was 110 ± 10 minutes for partial anterior fundoplication and was 120 ± 19.01 minutes for floppy Nissen

Table (2): Mean operative time among studied group

Operative time	Studied group		t- test	P value
	Group I	Group II		
$\bar{X} \pm SD$	100±10	120 ± 19.01	12.19	<0.001

X: mean; SD: standard deviation; t: t test

Table (3): Total score of heartburn among studied group

Total score of dysphagia	Studied group		t-test	P value
	Group I $\bar{X} \pm SD$	Group II $\bar{X} \pm SD$		
Preoperative	2.8±2.7	2.5±3.7	0.25	>0.05
Postoperative				
- 3 months	5.2±1.8	8.6±2.6	3.9	<0.001
- 6 months	3.4±1.1	4.8±2.3	2.1	>0.05
- 12 months	1.9±0.36	2.1±0.9	0.7	>0.05

Table (4): Difference in total score of dysphagia among studied group

Total score of dysphagia	Studied group		t-test	P value
	Group I $\bar{X} \pm SD$	Group II $\bar{X} \pm SD$		
Preoperative	2.8±2.7	2.5±3.7	0.25	>0.05
Postoperative				
- 3 months	5.2±1.8	8.6±2.6	3.9	<0.001
- 6 months	3.4±1.1	4.8±2.3	2.1	>0.05
- 12 months	1.9±0.36	2.1±0.9	0.7	>0.05

Gas bloating was significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) in group II than in group I all the period of follow up table (5).

fundoplication. There was significant difference between both groups as regards the operative time in favor of partial anterior wrap. This may be due to longer time needed for short gastric dissection. The mean operative time in the present study seems to be longer when compared with that of [Watson et al \(1999\)](#), who recorded mean Operative time for the two procedures (58 min) for Nissen (range 32-184 min) procedure versus 60 min for anterior fundoplication (range 35-144 min), and with that of [Chrysos et al \(2001\)](#), who recorded 100 ± 22 min for Nissen fundoplication. Also [Chrysos et al \(2003\)](#), again recorded 67 ± 15 minutes. [Kneist et al \(2003\)](#), reported mean operative time 90 min for partial anterior fundoplication. On the other hand, mean operative time in the present study seems to be slightly shorter when compared with that of [Peters et al \(1998\)](#), who recorded 202 ± 58 min for Nissen fundoplication. After 3, 6, 12 months a standardized score was used to assess the clinical improvement of the symptoms after operations (heartburn and regurgitation) and revealed that both partial anterior and Nissen

fundoplication are effective in controlling heartburn and regurgitation with significant difference between both groups after 3 months in favor of Nissen but after 6 & 12 months follow up there was no significant difference between both groups.

After 3 months in group I (partial anterior) about 70% of reflux symptoms was controlled but in group II (Nissen) about 90% of reflux symptoms were controlled, The percent has raised in both groups at the end of the study to reach about 95% in group I ,98% in group II. This means that Nissen fundoplication is more effective in controlling reflux symptoms in the early postoperative but on long term follow up no significant difference between both groups. The results of our study match with that of [Baigrie et al \(2005\)](#), who recorded a reflux control of about 90% in anterior hemi fundoplication patients after 2 years and nearly 100% after Nissen fundoplication .In another study performed by [Watson et al \(1999\)](#), revealed similar clinical outcome after 3 months follow up after both procedures.

Table (5): Difference in total score of gas bloating between both groups postoperatively

Total score of gas bloating postoperative	Studied group		t- test	P- value
	Group I $\bar{X} \pm SD$	Group II $\bar{X} \pm SD$		
Postoperative				
- 3 months	7.1±3.1	13.2±2.8	0.8	<0.001
- 6months	0.2±0.4	6.3±1.4	15.7	<0.001
- 12months	0.1±0.3	3.1±0.6	14.8	<0.001

Table (6): Difference in improvement in manometric study of both groups 6 months post operatively

Difference of improvement	Difference of improvement		P value
	Group I $\bar{X} \pm SD$	Group II $\bar{X} \pm SD$	
LES pressure(mmHg)	8.3±0.14	11.6±0.9	<0.001
LES residual pressure(mmHg)	5.1±0.7	9.4±2.4	<0.001
LES over length(cm)	0.6±0.08	0.5±0.01	>0.05
LES abdominal length(cm)	1.3±0.19	1.3±0.01	>0.05
Amplitude of esophageal body contraction(mmHg)	4±0.63	3±2.91	<0.05

Table (7): Difference of improvement in 24 hours PH monitoring of both groups 6 months postoperatively.

24hr PH monitoring	Improvement		t-test	P value
	Group I $\bar{X}\pm SD$	Group II $\bar{X}\pm SD$		
Percent of total time PH<4	5.3±0.36	7.6 ±0.52	11.5	<0.001
Percent of upright time PH<4	3.9±0.78	4.9±1.06	2.4	<0.02
Percent of supine time PH<4	1.6±0.32	3.2±0.02	15.1	<0.001
N. of episodes PH<4	86±0.66	87±0.23	4.5	<0.001
N. of episodes PH<4 and lasting>5 min	11.5±5.2	12.5±9.1	0.3	>0.05

Another study performed by [Nijjar et al \(2010\)](#), revealed a different result at 5 years' follow-up, mean analog scores for heartburn were 2.2 for anterior fundoplication versus 0.9 for Nissen fundoplication (P=.003). This means at long term follow up better control of reflux symptoms. This may be due to that our study was a short term follow up. On the other hand [Watson et al \(2004\)](#), published another study demonstrating a better reflux control at short term follow up (6 months) after Nissen fundoplication over anterior fundoplication. This may be due to larger number of the included patients in the study (112 patients). Regarding the onset of postoperative dysphagia in our study, it was higher in Nissen group and was significantly different at 3months follow up, at 6&12 months onset of dysphagia has decreased in Nissen group but still higher in comparison to partial anterior group.

Our result correlates with [Watson et al \(1999\)](#), who recorded less onset of dysphagia after 6 months follow up among patients who had undergone partial anterior rather than Nissen. On the same way. [Kneist et al. \(2003\)](#), in Germany also reported a good reflux control and less incidence of dysphagia after partial anterior fundoplication. In a similar fashion [Watson et al \(2004\)](#), found a lower percent of dysphagia in partial anterior group. Also in [Baigrie \(2005\)](#), recorded a less onset of dysphagia for both solids

&fluids after anterior fundoplication rather than in Nissen.

In a study published by [Fein and Seyfried \(2010\)](#), they recorded a higher incidence of dysphagia in Nissen patients but this was weighted against a higher rate of recurrent symptoms in anterior group patients. This may be due to multiple studies included in that study and longer period of follow up.

[Nijjar et al \(2010\)](#) published a study at 2010 recording no difference in dysphagia scores between the two groups and this was after 5 years follow up. [Ma et al \(2012\)](#) reported that there was a significant reduction of the incidence of postoperative dysphagia in patients with partial fundoplication (P < 0.0001). [Broeders et al, \(2013\)](#) stated a similar result. As regarding to gas bloating our study found that it was more among patients with Nissen rather than partial anterior group.similar to us [Watson et al \(1991\)](#) recorded in his study no gas bloat or inability to belch after partial anterior fundoplication. Also in [Ma et al \(2012\)](#) they reported a decreased incidence of inability to belch in partial fundoplication. In [Broeders et al. \(2013\)](#), study they reported a lower incidence of gas related symptoms (bloating, flatulence, inability to belch) in partial anterior group in comparison to Nissen group. On the other hand in [Cai et al. \(2008\)](#) study at 2008, there was no difference between the two groups.

This may be due to longer period of follow up (10years). Esophago-gastroscopy was performed to all patients in the present study in both groups at 3 months postoperatively and revealed that both procedures were effective in healing esophagitis with a percent of 71% & 80% for group I and group II respectively. Also [Watson \(1991\)](#) in one study at 1991, recorded endoscopic improvement in 95% and complete cure in 75% in patients after partial anterior fundoplication. [Watson et al. \(1998\)](#), recorded similar healing of esophagitis among both groups. Similarly [Watson et al \(2004\)](#) reported similar results of endoscopy for both groups. [Broeders et al \(2013\)](#) in their study at 2013, recorded healing of esophagitis 71% in (LAF) versus 77% in laparoscopic Nissen fundoplication (LNF).

As regards to postoperative manometric study of the esophagus in the present study, the mean resting LES pressure of Group I increased from 6.7 ± 2.32 mmHg to 15 ± 2.18 mmHg and that of Group II increased from 7.4 ± 1.35 mmHg to 19 ± 2.21 mmHg. The mean residual LES pressure after sphincter relaxation of Group I increased from $.7 \pm 1.1$ mmHg to 5.8 ± 1.8 mmHg while that of Group II increased from $.8 \pm 0.35$ to 10.2 ± 2.8 mmHg. Our results correlate with that of [Watson et al \(1991, 1995\)](#) .have reported at 1991 and at 1995 that manometric study after partial anterior fundoplication brings LES parameters to a more physiological state rather than total fundoplication. In 1998 [Watson et al \(1988\)](#) comparative study between (LAF) & (LNF) recorded resting and residual lower esophageal sphincter pressures were lower following anterior fundoplication (29 versus 18 mmHg, and 13 versus 6 mmHg). [Broeders et al \(2013\)](#) and [Watson et al. \(2004\)](#) both reported similar improvement after both procedures with no significant difference unlike to our study but this may be due to the longer period of follow up (5years) in the first study. And the higher number of patients in the second study (102) patient. As regards 24 hours pH monitoring in this study, the test was performed six months postoperatively in only ten patients of each group. The mean percent total time pH < 4 dropped from $10.8 \pm 1.5\%$ to $5.5 \pm 1.14\%$ in

Group I and from 10.5 ± 1.5 to $2.9 \pm 0.98\%$ in Group II and there was a significant difference between both groups making floppy Nissen fundoplication more superior than partial anterior fundoplication in improving the parameters of 24 hours pH metery. This correlates with clinical outcome in both groups that heartburn scores improved better in Nissen group .And also objectively esophagitis healed better in Nissen group. Our result correlates with the result that [Watson et al. \(1995\)](#), had published in their study on patients with (LAF) that revealed a normal esophageal pH profile.

The mean percentage of total time that pH < 4 falling from 11.0 to 1.1 (P < 0.001). With the same result [Varin et al \(2009\)](#), published results similar of significant difference in favor of (LAF) regarding dysphagia & gas related symptoms with no significant difference in heartburn, acid reflux or esophagitis. [Watson \(2012\)](#) published another study reporting that partial anterior fundoplication was accompanied with less side effects and achieved similar results to Nissen. In [Broeders et al \(2013\)](#) illustrated a more esophageal acid exposure in (LAF) group than (LNF) group and subsequently more esophagitis among (LAF). Subjectively, both partial anterior and Nissen fundoplication are effective in controlling clinical symptoms of GERD (heartburn and regurgitation) with no significant difference between the two procedures with time at (6-12 months).

The incidence of postoperative dysphagia was higher with floppy Nissen fundoplication, the difference was significant early between the two procedures but with time the difference had decreased but still higher, also partial anterior fundoplication is more superior with significant difference in decreasing the incidence of gas related symptoms. Objectively, although partial anterior fundoplication improved the characters of LES on manometric study to the normal level, Nissen fundoplication is more superior with significant difference in improving the characters of LES on manometric study and parameters of 24 hours pH monitoring.

CONCLUSION

Partial anterior fundoplication seems safe and effective in treating the symptoms of GERD as Nissen fundoplication including patients with severe forms of the disease. Its technique is simpler and takes shorter time to perform. Lower postoperative sequelae with partial anterior fundoplication as regards dysphagia and gas related symptoms. Further evaluation of partial anterior fundoplication should be done with more number of cases and longer period of follow up to give more conclusive idea about the procedure and its drawback claimed by those who are against (recurrence of symptoms on long term follow up).

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